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Fully-Woven Textile Implementation of a Circularly Polarized Rectenna for Wireless Power Transfer Applications

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ABSTRACT This work describes a fully-woven textile rectenna for Wireless Power Transfer applications in the 2.4 GHz frequency band. The radiating element is based on a square patch fed through an offset T-match network to which the rectifier is connected. This feeding structure provides impedance matching with the rectifier without requiring additional networks, which results in a compact layout. On the other hand, its particular location at one or the patch corners is exploited to generate circular polarization. The rectifier is based on a single Schottky diode to provide a layout suitable for textile integration. It is mounted on a carrier thread which is then woven together with the rest of the textile structure of the antenna, providing a large degree of integration and robustness. The measured RF-DC conversion efficiency is about 50% for -10 dBm available power at the rectifier input, which is comparable to state-of-the-art values reported for rectennas implemented in conventional rigid substrates, demonstrating the viability of woven technology in the microwave frequency band. Furthermore, the frequency weighted and the power frequency weighted conversion efficiency figures of merit were evaluated, showing a considerably improvement with respect to previously reported works.

INDEX TERMS Antennas, rectenna, rectifier, textile technology, wireless power transfer.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, wearable technologies have attracted the interest of the scientific and the industrial communities. One of the reasons is the large number of potential applications related to sensing vital signs in different fields, such as sports or healthcare, as those presented in [1] and [2], in which wearable devices are used to monitor the breath rate and to transmit data to a cortical visual prosthesis, respectively. However, some challenges still need addressing, among which the DC powering of the sensors and the circuitry integration on a really wearable device can be considered to be the most relevant [3].

Regarding the DC powering challenge, Energy Harvesting (EH) and Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) technologies have

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been proposed as very promising approaches to avoid the use of batteries in low power applications [3]. EH is based on gathering electromagnetic energy originated in nondedicated sources, such as Wi-Fi access points, mobile phone base stations, and radio or TV transmitters [4], [5], [6]. Thus, the available power levels are dependent on the location, and wide-band and/or multi-band rectennas are required. On the other hand, in WPT systems, a dedicated narrowband source is used as remote power source, which provides a more constant and predictable available power values [7], and eases the rectenna design, providing, in general, better performance than EH.

Considering the integration of remotely powered wearable devices, most of the design effort should be focused on the rectenna, because of the large area of the radiating element. From this point of view, when compared to conventional RF manufacturing technologies, the use of textile technology

provides some advantages, such as inherent flexibility, certain degree of breathability, and ease of integration in fabric pieces. Several different nonwoven approaches for the implementation of textile rectennas have been reported in the last few years, based on concealing a flexible rectenna in a fabric pocketed [8], stacking several shaped conductive and dielectric fabric pieces [9], [10], [11], combining textile and conventional substrates [12], [13], and embroidering with conductive thread on dielectric fabric sheets [14], [15], [16]. Although all the cited works achieve good electrical performance, the used nonwoven technologies still present some issues to be addressed. On the one hand, the rectifier is implemented by soldering lumped electronic components to textile pads, or using a conventional rigid PCB substrate which is then soldered to the textile part. On the other hand, the described technologies use several different layers and elements that must be attached between them. Thus, all the devices exhibit a moderate degree of integration and robustness.

The use of fully-woven textile technology for the implementation of antennas and other RF devices has also been described. This approach was applied to the development of frequency selective surfaces [17], [18], general purpose antennas [19], [20], LF and UHF RFID tags [21], [22], and rectennas [23], [24]. In the case of [21], [22], [23], and [24], the required circuitry was incorporated to the woven textile structure by using carrier threads, which provides the best degree of integration described to date, and improved robustness, since no soldered unions with textile parts are required. Furthermore, when compared with nonwoven approaches, the fully-woven technology provides some key advantages, such as a better integration with fabric supports, the capability of large-scale production using machinery from the textile industry, and improved robustness, since the entire multilayer textile structure is implemented as a unique fabric piece, instead of being composed of several independent layers attached between them. In addition to these advantages, the reported electrical performance of fully-woven devices is comparable to the state of the art for other nonwoven textile, and even to conventional manufacturing technologies, which makes this approach a good alternative for the development of wearable applications.

In this work, a textile fully-woven circularly polarized rectenna for WPT applications in the 2.4 GHz band is presented. It combines a radiating element, based on a square patch fed through a T-match structure [25], with a rectifier integrated with the woven structure using a carrier thread [22], [23], [24], which allows to obtain a large degree of integration and robustness. The main novelty of the work is related with the location of the feeding network, connected to two adjacent patch edges, close to the corresponding corner, which simultaneously provides complex conjugate matching with the rectifier and circular polarization, while obtaining a compact and geometrically simple layout compatible with the fully-woven implementation. To the best of the

FIGURE 1. Rectenna topology and structure. a) Top and front view. b) Topology of the single Schottky diode based rectifier. c) Fully-woven textile multilayer structure. Binder threads are depicted in blue.

author's knowledge, this is the first time that the proposed feeding technique is reported. Furthermore, the measured performance improves the state of the art for textile rectennas.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the topology and the woven structure of the proposed antenna. In section III, the design process of the antenna and the rectifier is outlined. Section IV provides some details about the implementation. The experimental results are presented and analyzed in section V.

II. TOPOLOGY AND WOVEN STRUCTURE

A. RECTENNA TOPOLOGY

Figure 1 schematizes the topology of the proposed textile rectenna. It is composed of a radiating element and a single-diode rectifier, which are specifically conceived to be implemented in fully-woven technology.

The radiating element is a nearly square patch fed through a distributed T-match structure [25]. As described in [25], and represented in Fig. 1 a), it is composed of two transmission line segments, with one end connected to the radiating element, and the other one acting as a port terminal. This feeding technique simultaneously provides complex conjugate impedance matching with the rectifier and circular polarization, since its location at the patch corner introduces a length difference between the two patch diagonals, which results in two orthogonal modes with slightly different resonant frequencies. The obtained layout is compact and suitable to be implemented in fully-woven textile technology. Furthermore, it is compatible with the technique used to integrate the rectifier with the textile structure [23], since the two terminals are on the same plane, while the inherent ground plane isolates the antenna performance from the underneath surface or body [24], which is a valuable characteristic for wearable devices.

Regarding the rectifier, a single Schottky diode topology similar to that described in [23] was selected to obtain a layout simple enough to be integrated into the textile antenna using a carrier thread, and to maximize the RF-DC power conversion under low input available power conditions.

B. WOVEN STRUCTURE

The rectenna is conceived to be implemented on the fully-woven textile structure schematized in Fig. 1 c), which is composed of two conductive layers woven with silver coated polyamide *ELITEX 117/f17 2ply* threads, and separated by a dielectric layer woven with polyester threads. All the layers are held together with polyester binder threads, which are woven at the same time as the rest of the structure, providing an indivisible multilayer fabric piece with improved robustness when compared with other textile nonwoven approaches. The layout of the antenna is patterned on one of the conductive layers, while the other one acts as the ground plane.

To reduce the geometrical and computational complexity while preserving the EM simulation accuracy of the textile structure [26], [27], the dielectric layer is modeled as an equivalent homogeneous sheet with the same thickness h_{diel} , equivalent dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_{r,eq} \approx 1.8$, and $\tan \delta \approx 0.04$. These values were estimated from the experimental characterization of a transmission line and a resonator, implemented on the same fabric as the antenna. Note that the equivalent dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_{r,eq} \approx 1.8$ is reduced with respect to the $\epsilon_r = 4.1$ value of the polyester from which the threads are extruded because of the air gaps contained in the woven structure, which depends on the loom setup.

Regarding the conductive layers, they can also be modeled as homogeneous sheets because a large number of electrical contacts between warp and weft threads is generated at the weaving process, allowing the current to flow in any direction, and because the $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ skin depth on the silver coating at 2.4 GHz is larger than the $1 \mu\text{m}$ coating thickness of each individual thread. Thus, the equivalent layer thickness is the same as the silver coating thickness of the threads, $h_{cond} = 1 \mu\text{m}$, and the equivalent conductivity is $\sigma_{eq} = 6.3 \times 10^7 \text{ S/m}$, similar to that of the thread silver coating.

III. RECTENNA DESIGN

To maximize the power transfer between the antenna and the rectifier, complex conjugate impedance matching between them, $Z_a = Z_r^*$, should be achieved. A co-simulation strategy is carried out. First, the input impedance Z_r of the rectifier, under the considered working conditions, is calculated through Harmonic Balance (HB) simulations, using the commercial CAD software package *Advanced Design System*, from *Keysight*. Then, the antenna is modeled in *Ansys HFSS*, and optimized to achieve $Z_a = Z_r^*$. Furthermore, by combining the data from the two simulation techniques, the impact of impedance variations on the overall behavior of the rectenna can be analyzed.

A. RECTIFIER

Figure 1 b) shows the rectifier topology. It includes a single *Infineon BAT15-04W* Schottky diode, a $C = 1 \text{ nF}$ shunt capacitor to short-circuit the RF signal at the diode output, and a $L = 6.4 \text{ nH}$ input series inductor to partially

FIGURE 2. Influence of the real, R_a , and the imaginary, X_a , parts of the antenna input impedance, Z_a , on the system RF-DC conversion efficiency η , when the available power at the rectifier input is $P_{RF} = -10 \text{ dBm}$.

compensate for the high capacitive part of the rectifier input impedance Z_r . A resistor R is used to emulate the rectifier load. As shown in [23], the output DC voltage, V_{DC} , increases with the value of R , but the RF-DC conversion efficiency η (1) decreases. Here, $R = 5.1 \text{ k}\Omega$ was selected to obtain a good trade-off between the two parameters.

$$\eta(\%) = \frac{V_{DC}^2}{R \times P_{RF}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The circuit performance was analyzed through nonlinear simulations based on the Harmonic Balance (HB) technique. It was driven by an input RF signal with frequency $f_{RF} = 2.4 \text{ GHz}$, and available power $P_{RF} = -10 \text{ dBm}$, which is considered to be a realistic value when taking into account the EIRP limitations for indoor transmitters and the free space propagation losses. Under the described working conditions, the calculated input impedance, evaluated at $f_{RF} = 2.4 \text{ GHz}$, is $Z_r = 13 - j88 \Omega$, while the maximum RF-DC conversion efficiency η is about 60%.

Figure 2 represents the impact of the impedance mismatching between the antenna and the rectifier on the RF-DC conversion efficiency. It was obtained in simulation, by sweeping the real and the imaginary parts of the output impedance of the signal source used to drive the rectifier, which plays the same role as the antenna input impedance Z_a . As expected, the maximum η value is reached when $Z_a = Z_r^* = 13 + j88 \Omega$. Furthermore, the conversion efficiency is larger than 50% for a 20Ω variation about the optimum impedance in both the real and the imaginary parts. This ensures an acceptable performance under moderate deviations of the antenna input impedance from the optimum value, $Z_a = Z_r^*$, related to the limited geometrical accuracy that can be achieved when working with textile structures, and to potential deformations of the antenna under real use conditions in a wearable application.

B. ANTENNA

The radiating element is based on a nearly square patch sized to resonate at about 2.4 GHz. The selected feeding technique provides an input impedance Z_a with low real part and large inductive imaginary part, which are required to

FIGURE 3. Variation of the simulated antenna input impedance Z_a with the loop length $l = l_1 + 2l_2$.

TABLE 1. Optimized parameters.

Parameter	L_p	l_1	l_2	g	c	h_{diel}	h_{cond}
Value (mm)	41	5.7	3.2	1.5	5.5	0.81	0.001

match the input impedance of the rectifier $Z_a = Z_r^*$. The width of the arms of the T-match network, w , was set to 2 mm, and the port width, p , was set to 6 mm to generate space for the rectifier. From a parametric analysis it is observed that both the real and the imaginary parts of Z_a increase with the total loop length, i. e., when increasing l_1 , l_2 , and/or g . The evolution of Z_a with frequency is represented in Fig. 3. The obtained value at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz is $Z_a = 13.4 + j86.5 \Omega$, which, when using combined with the previously described rectifier, should provide a RF-DC conversion efficiency close to 60%. Table 1 shows the value of the optimized parameters. Note that the evaluation of the reflection coefficient over a 50Ω load does not provide relevant information in this case because Z_a is very different from 50Ω , since it is designed to match the rectifier input impedance, $Z_a = Z_r^*$, without requiring additional networks.

The main novelty of the work is related with the location of the feeding network, connected to two adjacent patch edges, close to the corresponding corner. Because of the location, two orthogonal modes are excited, with slightly different resonant frequencies due to the length difference between the two patch diagonals created by the presence of the feeding network. Thus, the proposed feeding technique simultaneously provides complex conjugate matching with the rectifier and circular polarization, providing a compact and geometrically simple layout compatible with the fully-woven implementation.

Figure 4 a) represents normalized RHCP and LHCP components of the radiation pattern, evaluated at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz. The evolution of the axial ratio with the frequency, evaluated at $\theta = 0^\circ$, is shown in Fig.4 b). It is under 3 dB in the 2.37-2.42 GHz range, in which the value of Z_a varies from $13.9 + j84 \Omega$ to $15.6 + j86 \Omega$, that should provide efficiency values larger than 55%. Note that the minimum value of the axial ratio should be reached at a frequency point between the resonant frequencies of the two excited orthogonal modes.

FIGURE 4. a) Simulated radiation pattern, evaluated at 2.4 GHz. b) Evolution of the axial ratio with the working frequency, evaluated at the $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction. c) Simulated evolution of the radiation efficiency and the maximum gain with frequency. Continuous line: free space. Dashed line: Effect of the human body proximity.

In this case, it occurs at a frequency slightly different from 2.4 GHz because obtaining an input impedance Z_a as close as possible to Z_r^* was prioritized. Finally, Fig. 4 c) represents the evolution of the gain and the radiation efficiency with frequency, showing a gain value slightly larger than 0 dB and a radiation efficiency value about 20 % at 2.4 GHz. These values, which are small for a conventional patch antenna, are due to the relatively large loss tangent of the dielectric fabric layer used as substrate.

C. EFFECT OF HUMAN BODY PROXIMITY

Since one of the possible applications of the presented rectenna is to be used in wearable devices, the effect of the human body proximity on the antenna performance was numerically evaluated. The antenna was placed over a multilayer human tissue model [28], composed of skin, fat, muscle and bone, as schematized in the inset of Fig. 4 b). The thickness and the electrical parameters of each layer are shown in Table 2, and the side length was set to 200 mm, slightly smaller than $\lambda/2$ at 2.4 GHz. Furthermore, to take into account the effect of a garment between the antenna and the body, a 2 mm thickness layer with the same electrical parameters as those used to model the dielectric layer of the antenna was placed between the antenna and the body model.

The impact of the human body proximity on the input impedance Z_a and the radiation properties of the antenna is

TABLE 2. Electrical parameters of the layers in the human body model.

	Skin	Fat	Muscle	Bone
ϵ_r	37	5.2	51.5	10.8
σ (S/m)	2.02	0.16	2.56	0.61
Thickness (mm)	3	7	20	10

FIGURE 5. Picture of the implemented prototype.

represented in Figs. 3 and 4. As expected for a radiating structure with a large enough continuous ground plane, small deviations from the free space operation are observed. In the case of Z_a , the variation is smaller than 3Ω in both the real and the imaginary parts, with negligible impact on the RF-DC conversion efficiency. Similar conclusions can be extracted about the radiation pattern, the gain, and the polarization properties.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation procedure is similar to that reported in [23]. Starting from the previously described multilayer fabric piece, the layout of the antenna was patterned on one of the conductive layers through a laser cutting process. At this step, although the accuracy of the cutting process can be considered to be ideal, the achieved geometrical accuracy is limited by the conductive thread diameter, which imposed the minimum strip width that can be removed.

On the other hand, the rectifier was implemented on a flexible RF substrate, and then attached to a carrier thread which is woven with the textile structure of the antenna, generating a large number of electrical contact points between the rectifier and the antenna terminals, without soldering [22], [23]. In this way, the robustness and the integration degree are improved, and large-scale production using industrial looms is possible. A picture of the prototype is shown in Fig. 5.

V. EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION

To evaluate the prototype performance, a transmitter composed of a signal source and a linearly polarized patch antenna, with gain $G_{TX} \approx 4$ dB, was used. The power of the signal source was set to $P_{TX} = 23$ dBm in order to comply with the EIRP European regulation for indoor ISM transmitters. A realistic scenario was emulated by setting the distance between the transmitter and the rectenna to 0.5 m,

FIGURE 6. a) Measured output DC voltage V_{DC} for different available power values at the rectifier input. b) Measured output DC power P_{DC} for different available power values at the rectifier input. Continuous trace: Undeformed rectenna. Dashed trace: Bent rectenna. Dot trace: Effect of human body proximity.

for which the free space propagation losses, evaluated at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz, are around 34 dB. Since it is difficult to accurately measure the antenna gain, because its input impedance is not matched to 50Ω , the 0 dB simulated value is considered. Furthermore, an additional 3 dB loss factor due to the polarization mismatch between the linearly polarized transmitter antenna and the circularly polarized rectenna has to be included. Taking into account all the indicated factors, the estimated available power at the rectifier input is $P_{RF} \approx -10$ dBm. At the receiver side, the rectified DC voltage V_{DC} is measured at the resistor terminals, from which the rectified DC power P_{DC} can be easily calculated. A non anechoic laboratory environment was considered in order to obtain results as close as possible to a real use scenario.

The measured output DC voltage V_{DC} and power P_{DC} , and the computed RF-DC conversion efficiency, are represented in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. The maximum DC power value $P_{DC} \approx 50 \mu\text{W}$ is achieved around 2.4 GHz, showing that the optimum impedance matching between the antenna and the rectifier is reached at that frequency. The maximum measured efficiency value is slightly smaller than that predicted in simulation, which could be due to inaccuracies in the large-signal model of the diode, and/or to a variation of the antenna gain with respect to the 0 dB considered value. This measurement uncertainty was addressed by testing the rectenna for other distance values, in order to analyze its practical viability. The considered distances are 0.3, 0.65, and 0.8 m, for which the estimated available RF power values at the rectifier input, assuming a 0 dB antenna gain, are -6 , -12 , and -14 dBm, respectively. Note that the DC voltage and power, which are the relevant magnitudes from a practical point of view, can be accurately measured, whereas the available power at the rectifier input, which can be estimated but not accurately evaluated because of the antenna gain uncertainty, is only required to evaluate the RF-DC

TABLE 3. Comparison with the state of the art for textile rectennas.

Ref.	Frequency (GHz)	η (%)	Available Power P_{RF} (dBm)	Polarization	Axial Ratio BW (%)	FE	PFE	Technology
[9]	0.82	42	-20	Dual Linear	-	34.5	54.6	Stacked fabric layers
[11]	0.82	62	-	Linear	-	-	-	Stacked fabric layers
[8]	1	30	-10	Linear	-	30	37.8	Concealed conventional PCB
[10]	2.45	30	-10	Linear	-	73.5	92.6	Stacked fabric layers
[12]	2.45	56	-5	Circular	2.3	137.2	154	Hybrid PCB/textile layers
[15]	2.45	35	-10	Linear	-	85.8	108	Embroidering
[23]	2.4	45	-10	Circular	1.6	108	134	Fully-woven
This work	2.4	50	-10	Circular	2.1	120	151	Fully-woven

FIGURE 7. Measured RF-DC conversion efficiency for different available power values at the rectifier input. Continuous trace: Undeformed rectenna. Dashed trace: Bent rectenna. Dot trace: Effect of human body proximity.

FIGURE 8. Normalized DC power P_{DC} for different rotation angles.

conversion efficiency. As can be expected, the conversion efficiency reduces with the available power, because of the inherent characteristics of Schottky diodes, but it is still higher than 40% for $P_{RF} = -14$ dBm, at 0.8 m from the transmitter.

To check that the rectenna is circularly polarized, it was rotated around the z axis (see Fig. 1) from 0° to 90° , with 15° step, measuring for each rotation angle the P_{DC} value, at $f_{RF} = 2.37, 2.4,$ and 2.42 GHz. This is equivalent to rotate the linearly polarized incident electric field vector with respect to the rectenna. Since the available RF power P_{RF} at the antenna terminals depends on the relative orientation of the incident electric field vector with respect to the rectenna, and the measured rectified power P_{DC} is proportional to P_{RF} , this measurement approach allows to experimentally evaluate the axial ratio of the rectenna as the difference between the maximum and the minimum values of the measured P_{DC} . Figure 8 displays the results, showing a power variation around 3 dB. Thus, it can be concluded that the rectenna exhibits circular polarization.

Finally, the performance of the rectenna was evaluated under conditions closer to real wearable applications than free space operation. On the one hand, to analyze the impact of potential deformations on the rectenna performance, which can occur in a wearable application because of the inherent flexibility of the woven structure, the rectenna was bent along the x axis with 20 cm radius. The results are represented in Figs. 6, 7, and 8, together with the measurements of the undeformed rectenna, showing that the behavior is stable

against moderate deformations. Furthermore, it is observed that the variation of the measured V_{DC} and P_{DC} values around the center working frequency is smoother when bending the antenna, which could be due to a slight variation of the input impedance. On the other hand, the rectenna was placed over the torso of a volunteer. The measured DC voltage, power, and the RF-DC conversion efficiency are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. Because the inherent ground plane of the selected radiating structure and, as can be predicted from the simulation data, the human body proximity has no appreciable influence on the rectenna performance.

VI. COMPARISON WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Table 3 compares the performance of the presented prototype with the state of the art for textile rectennas. With the exception of [23], this work is the only one using fully-woven technology, which improves the robustness and the degree of integration, since the whole multilayer structure of the rectenna is manufactured as an indivisible fabric piece. Furthermore, the technique used to attach the rectifier to the antenna does not require soldered unions with textile pads and provides the maximum degree of integration.

Since the compared rectennas work at different frequency bands, and with different input power levels, the frequency weighted efficiency (FE) and the power/frequency weighted efficiency (PFE) figures of merit [29], [30], have been calculated using (2) and (3), respectively, to obtain a global performance overview.

$$FE = \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i \times f_{RF,i}^{0.25} \quad (2)$$

$$PFE = \frac{1}{P_{RF}^{0.1}} \times FE \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of frequency bands (in this case, $n = 1$), $f_{RF,i}$ is the center frequency of each band, expressed in GHz, η_i is the RF-DC conversion efficiency, and P_{RF} is the available power at the rectifier input, expressed in mW.

The measured performance of the design presented in this work considerably improves most of the previously reported textile rectennas. In the case of [12], a slightly larger value of FE is achieved, but the required input power is -5 dBm, which corresponds to an unrealistic practical scenario, from the point of view of the required transmitter EIRP and/or the maximum possible distance between the transmitter and the rectenna.

The actual work, [12], and [23] describe rectennas with circular polarization, which contributes to minimize the variation of the rectified power when the relative orientation of the rectenna with respect to the transmitter antenna cannot be controlled. The achieved relative 3 dB axial ratio bandwidth noticeably improves that reported for the textile fully-woven rectenna presented in [23]. On the other hand, it is slightly smaller than in [12], in which a more complex nonwoven structure combined with a rigid PCB is used, lacking the advantages of fully-woven technology.

The previous comparison shows that the presented design, whose novelty lies on the location of the feeding network, is able to improve the state of the art for textile woven and nonwoven rectennas, in terms of frequency and power weighted RF-DC conversion efficiency and axial ratio bandwidth, while preserving all the advantages of fully-woven textile technology.

VII. CONCLUSION

A 2.4 GHz fully-woven textile rectenna with a novel feeding technique intended for WPT applications was presented. The radiating element is a nearly square patch fed through a T-match network to which a single diode rectifier is connected. The proposed feeding technique simultaneously provides complex conjugate matching to the rectifier and circular polarization, because of its location. The resulting layout is compact, since no additional impedance matching networks are required, and compatible with the fully-woven textile technology and with the technique used to integrate the rectifier. Furthermore, by placing the feeding structure at one of the patch corners, circular polarization is achieved using only one port.

The measured RF-DC conversion efficiency is higher than 50% for a -10 dBm available power at the rectifier input, which is a realistic value, considering a transmitter with a 27 dBm EIRP, which fulfills the European regulations, located at 0.5 m from the rectenna. This value is in good agreement with simulation results, validating the design techniques. On the other hand, it is comparable to the state of the art for nonwoven textile implementations, and close to the values reported for rectennas implemented in conventional RF substrates.

The obtained experimental results show that the fully-woven textile technology can be exploited to design wearable RF devices with electrical performance comparable to the state of the art for other nonwoven textile approaches, while providing a set of valuable characteristics, i. e., improved robustness and integration level with electronics, ease of integration with larger textile elements, and the possibility of large-scale production using industrial looms.

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